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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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GEN TERAPIYASI TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Gen terapiyasining asosiy maqsadi nuqsonli va kasallik qo‘zg‘atuvchi genni sog‘lom gen bilan almashtirishdir. Gen terapiyasining maqsadi somatik, ya‘ni tana hujayrasi yoki jinsiy hujayra, ya‘ni tuxum yoki sperma bo‘lishi mumkin. Hozirgi vaqtda amaliyotda davolash usullari somatik hujayralarga qaratilgan bo‘lib, jinsiy hujayralar ustida ishlash axloqiy va qonuniy ravishda qabul qilinmaydi[1].

Kalit so‘zlar: Gen terapiyasi, retro virus, adeno virus, somatik terapiya, homila terapiyasi,immunitet.

50 yildan ko‘proq vaqt oldin olimlar DNK ning genetik modifikatsiyasi bilan inson genetik kasalliklarini samarali davolash imkoni borligi taxmin qilindi. Gen terapiyasining ushbu konsepsiyasi davolanishga chidamli kasalliklari bo‘lgan bemorlarda klinik yaxshilanish yoki to‘liq tiklanish mumkinligiga umid qilindi[2]. Istalgan genlarni maqsadli hujayraga yetkazish uchun bir nechta usullarni qo‘llash mumkin. Eng keng tarqalgan qo‘llanilishi gen transplantatsiyasi, ya‘ni yetishmayotgan yoki nuqsonli genni DNK ning istalgan joyiga oddiy genni kiritish orqali almashtirish. Gomologik rekombinatsiya deb ataladigan usulda hujayraning o‘z DNK sini tiklash qobiliyatidan foydalaniladi[1].

Gen terapiyasi 2 xil usulda amalga oshiriladi. Birinchi usul-somatik terapiya. Bu usul mutant genni sog‘lom gen bilan almashtirishga imkon beradi, bu sohada ayrim muvaffaqiyatli natijalarga ham erishildi. Somatik hujayralar irsiyatni o‘zgartirish natijasi faqat shu shaxs uchun 16-21 haftali pusht hujayralaridan foydalanadi. Gen terapiyasining ikkinchi usuli-homila terapiyasi bo‘lib bunda jinsiy hujayralar irsiy materialini o‘zgartiriladi. Bu o‘zgarishlar nasldan naslga o‘tadi. Shuning uchun ham homila terapiyasi 1994-yilda YUNESKO tomonidan qat‘iy taqiqlangan. Insonning reproduktiv funksiyalariga aralashish texnologiyalari kelajak avlodlarning taqdiri bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgani uchun, uning etnik tomonlarini chuqur tahlil qilish va qonuniy normativlarini ishlab chiqish lozim. Gametalarning gen terapiyasi keyingi avlodlar genomi o‘zgarishlarga olib kelishi ya‘ni mutatsiyalar kelib chiqishi, insoniyat jamiyat bilan atrof-muhit muvozanati buzilishiga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin[3].

Retro, adeno bilan bog‘liq viruslar gen terapiyasida eng ko‘p qo‘llaniladigan turlardir. Bundan tashqari, psevdotipli viruslar ham keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, ularning yuqtirish qobiliyati o‘zlarining qobiq oqsillari tuzilishini manipulatsiya qilish orqali

o'zgartirilgan. Retroviruslarning genetik materiali RNK shaklida bo'lib ular maqsadli hujayra ichiga kirib avvalo teskari transkripsiya orqali o'z RNK larining DNK nusxalarini yaratadilar, so'ngra ularni integraza fermenti bilan mezbon hujayraning genomiga qo'shadilar. Bunday hujayra bo'linganda, virus geni yangi hujayralarga o'tadi. Gen terapiyasi uchun yetishmayotgan yoki nuqsonli gen retrovirus genomiga qo'shilishi va maqsadli hujayralarga, masalan, saraton hujayralariga o'tkazilishi mumkin va hatto bu hujayralar ko'paygan taqdirda ham genning mahsulotlari endi har bir yangi hujayrada paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Buni amalga oshirayotganda, jarayon davomida o'rtadan muhim gen chiqariladi. Uni hosil bo'lgan yadrolarga o'tkazib bo'lmaydi. Buning uchun terapevtik genni tashuvchi adenovirusni kasal to'qimalarga bir necha marta va ko'proq miqdorda yuborish kerak. Adeno bilan bog'langan viruslar porvoviruslar oilasiga mansub va bir zanjirli DNK ga ega. Ushbu viruslarning eng katta afzalliklari shundaki, ular har doim o'z genlarini 19-xromosomaning sobit hududiga qo'shadilar, bu esa hech qanday patologiyaga olib kelmaydi. Bundan tashqari bu viruslar neyronlar kabi bo'linmaydigan hujayralarga ham kirishi mumkin. Boshqa tomondan, ular oz miqdordagi DNK ni olib yurishi va immunitet tizmining ushbu viruslar bilan kasallangan hujayralarni birinchi insoniy sinovlarida tanib olishi adeno bilan bog'liq viruslar bilan davolash imkoniyatlarini cheklaydi. Viruslarning maqsadli hujayralarni tanib olishlari va ularga yopishib olishlari va kirishlari ularning sirtlaridagi qobiq oqsillarining tuzilishlari bilan bog'liq. Ushbu qobiq tuzilishini o'zgartirishi orqali virus tan oladigan hujayra turlarini ko'paytirish yoki kamaytirish mumkin.

Xulosa. Gen terapiyasi inson salomatligini yaxshilashda katta salohiyatga ega bo'lib, irsiy kasalliklar, saraton, neyrodegenerativ va immun tizimi kasalliklarini davolashda qo'llaniladi. Ushbu usul inson genomiga ta'sir qilishi sababli, u yuqori texnologik, qimmat va ehtiyotkorlik talab qiladigan jarayondir. Shuningdek gen terapiyasi axloqiy va huquqiy masalalarni ham keltirib chiqaradi, chunki genlarni o'zgartirish kelajak avlodlarga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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